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First beam tests for low emittance rings

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ABSTRACT

This report describes the status of the activity of the beam tests initiated in the WP7 to support the development of the next generation of ultra-low emittance ring and prepare the commissioning of the new machines under construction or in advanced design stages. So far, two experimental tests were made at beneficiary and associate laboratories, concerning novel injection schemes in a BESSY-II/PSI collaboration and the operation of negative alpha lattice at KARA. Plans for the future activities will be presented.

ARIES Consortium, 2018

For more information on ARIES, its partners and contributors please see <http://aries.web.cern.ch>

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Executive summary

Experimental tests supporting the development of ultra-low emittance rings are proposed and carried out in the WP7 Rings for Ultra-low Emittance Rings (RULE). Such tests are meant to tackle the most challenging accelerator physics issues related to the operation of such rings. The Deliverable 7.1 consists in the actual execution of this series of tests and this report presents a summary of the experiment done, their rationale, the experimental set ups, the results obtained and the difficulties met. The problem tackled refer to novel injection schemes and the operation of rings with large negative momentum compaction factor.

1. Introduction

In recent years, the development of ultra-low emittance rings has been one of the major research topics in accelerator science and technology, driven by R&D in the field of damping rings, colliders and more recently diffraction limited light sources. The developments have been underpinned by more aggressive lattice designs based on multi-bend-achromats (MBA) and the technology associated especially with high gradient magnets and small vacuum tubes. Fig. 1.1 provides a survey of the most important project (red dots) with a comparison of presently operating machines (blue dots). Light sources play a preponderant role in these developments.

*Table 1.1: Survey of low emittance rings. The emittance over the square of the relativistic factor (ϵ_s/γ^2) is a measure of the aggressiveness of the lattice design. The circumference is a rough indication of the number of bending magnets accommodated in the ring [**B**]*

The development of such rings has numerous accelerator physics challenges related to the beam dynamics of the electron beam in such highly constrained lattices. The main ones are

- difficulties in injection due to the small dynamic aperture, tackled by novel injection schemes
- reduced beam lifetime (Touschek effect), due to the small momentum aperture, tackled with complex beam dynamics optimisation
- higher sensitivity to collective effects, small momentum compaction factor, intra-beam scattering (IBS), collective instabilities in potentially large impedance pipes
- commissioning, operation, correction and modelling of such lattices

Most, if not all, of these challenges are addressed in the WP7 tasks and build upon the previous experience of the Low Emittance Ring (LER) Network supported in EUCARD2. In ARIES WP7, Task 4.1 is specifically targeted to propose and coordinate the activities to tackle the most importance beam dynamics challenges by providing access to machines for experimental studies and testing new ideas. ARIES has strongly fostered this activity by supporting networking between the EU labs. Deliverable 7.1 consists of a report describing the first experimental tests connecting different laboratories in experimental activities carried out with dedicated machine time.

Two tests are discussed. The first one concerns the injection of an off energy bunch into the RF bucket at intermediate RF phases. This type of tests study the capture mechanism of a beam injected in an usual position if the longitudinal phase space. This idea underpins more complex injection schemes devised for off-energy injection in ultra-low emittance rings [**K**, **T**]. The second tests aims at exploring the beam dynamics in large negative momentum compaction lattices which have been proposed as a possible route to achieve ultra-low emittances.

Future work will continue in the coordination of such tests and activities related to the commissioning of such ultra-low emittance ring. In particular, a topical workshop dedicated to a review of commissioning strategies, software and diagnostics tools is planned in February 2019 at KIT.

2. Off-energy Injection studies at Bessy-II

Injection in ultra-low emittance rings is notoriously difficult due to the restricted apertures (both dynamics and momentum apertures, i.e. on-momentum and off-momentum). In fact, the optimisation of the apertures is the key problem in the design of ultra-low emittance rings. While old rings based on standard double-bend or triple-bend achromats (DBA or TBA) inject comfortably in 10-15 mm DA and 3-4% momentum aperture, ultra-low emittance rings hardly achieve such values. Indeed, the results of the optimisation studies carried out at many facilities, show clearly that the lower the emittance, the smaller the apertures available to store the beam. To give a measure of the difficulties, we report that the injection scheme presented in the SLS-II CDR [S] uses an anti-septum to allow injection in a dynamic aperture of less than 5mm. The problem of injecting an external beam in such lattices is therefore one of the key challenges. In this framework, Task 7.1 in WP7 is exclusively dedicated to the injection problem. A topical workshop held at BESSY Berlin and presented as ARIES Milestone MS33 [T], was held to discuss novel injection schemes and the technological advancement required, mostly in terms of development of fast kicker driven by fast high voltage pulsers. In task 7.4 we tackle the problem by proposing experimental tests on key ideas of the new injection method proposed [K].

One of the new injection mode into ultra low emittance rings proposed with the aim of passing the problem of the small dynamic aperture is the so-called off-energy injection. This idea has been used to devise several variants of these injection scheme which are currently under studies in different projects [K].

1.2 THE EXPERIMENT AT BESSY-II

Two machine shifts were performed at the BESSY-II synchrotron on 17th and 18th of June 2018 in addition to further beam time on 13th of February and 25th June 2018. The main team consisted of Peter Kuske, Ji Li (HZB) and Masamitsu Aiba (PSI).

In the future low emittance rings the traditional off-axis injection may not be applicable. Alternative longitudinal injection schemes have been proposed, where it is important to evaluate the longitudinal acceptance accurately. The main motivation for this experiment was to measure accurately the longitudinal acceptance of a ring and compare with the result of numerical simulations.

Measurements of the injection efficiency at BESSY-II were taken for various injection timing and energies to explore the 2D longitudinal acceptance of the machine. The injection efficiency was measured using two current transformers (CTs). One is located in the beam transport line from the booster to the storage ring, and the other in the storage ring. For the latter CT, the beam current is measured after one second since the beam injection. A Matlab [M2] script was running during the measurement that read out the beam current from two CTs, computed the injection efficiency, and wrote it out to an Epics channel continuously. Another application, which is one of standard

tools available in the BESSY's control room, varied the injection timing. The injection efficiency and the corresponding injection timing were recorded through the EPICS standard strip chart application. The scan of the injection timing was repeated for various injection beam energies to complete the scan over the longitudinal phase space.

The plot in Fig. 2.1 reports the results of the 2D scan visualising the longitudinal acceptance and the very good agreement with the simulations. It is interesting to note the shape of the RF bucket that acquires a characteristic “golf club” shape due to the combined effect of RF and synchrotron radiation. Although the injection efficiency in the tails is rather low (20%) the whole longitudinal acceptance was successfully measured. The measured acceptances are reproduced through one-dimensional tracking simulations when the RF bucket height is up to about 3%. The “shaft” of the golf club is the phase space area of interest for off-energy, off-timing, on-axis injection into the storage ring when a small dynamic aperture is available.

Parameters	Values
Circumference	240 m
Lattice	16 DBAs
Beam energy	1.7 GeV
Energy loss	320 keV/turn
Momentum compaction	7.4×10^{-4}
Fundamental RF frequency	500 MHz
Booster bunch length	~55 ps
Booster bunch energy spread	5.7×10^{-4}

Table. 2.1: parameters of the Bessy-II ring

The input parameters are taken from Table 2.1. The simulations and measurements agree quite well with the measured acceptances except for the case with an RF voltage of 2.0 MV. At the low and middle voltages (0.6 and 1.12MV), the golf-club was clearly observed both in measurements and simulations. Some injection beam particles were captured by the RF buckets even when the beam was injected between two RF buckets, i.e. into the “shaft” of the golf-club acceptance. It is noted that the booster bunch (the injected beam) may be too long to fit the shaft. This is at least partly the reason why the injection efficiency is rather low (about 20%) at the shaft location in time.

At high voltage (2.0 MV), the shaft disappeared in the measurement in contrast to the simulation. This may indicate that the off-energy transverse acceptance is not enough, given that the transverse motion is not included in the simulation. The particles injected at the shaft follow the edge of the RF bucket, reaching to about $\pm 4\%$ energy deviation several times before synchrotron oscillation is damped. The betatron oscillation can be unstable at this rather large energy deviation even though its amplitude is minimized through on-axis injection. The edge of the measured acceptance at the high RF voltage is not smooth, and the discontinuities correspond to the separate data sets from different days. This suggests that the off-energy transverse acceptance at around 4% energy deviation is sensitive to small changes in the machine, supporting the above discussion.

Fig. 2.1: Longitudinal acceptance measured (left) and simulated (right). The RF voltage was 0.6 MV (top), 1.12 MV (middle) and 2.0 MV (bottom)

The present test is not yet a full demonstration of the feasibility of the novel injection scheme proposed in [A]. In fact such scheme relies on the use of fast kickers that allow injection the beam in the ring without kicking out the rest of the stored beam. With an RF of 500 MHz such fast kickers would have to generate pulses shorter than 2 ns. These were unavailable at BESSY-II and is an active area of research and development for the field. However the experimental test showed

that there are no fundamental limitations in the longitudinal dynamics for such scheme and provide a first major step in the development of such new injection scheme.

3. Operation with negative alpha lattices at KARA

The so-called Multi-Bend Achromat (MBA) lattice structure that allows for a significant reduction of the horizontal emittance as compared to the existing third generation storage rings, utilizes the principle that the minimal theoretical horizontal emittance scales with third power of the inverse of the number of dipoles in the ring. The resultant lattice generally suffers, however, from small horizontal dispersion, which in turn generates as a by-product a small momentum compaction factor α . Another effective scheme of emittance reduction proposed in the last years introduces the so-called reversed bends into the ring to decouple the focusing of the horizontal dispersion from the horizontal betatron function. While the scheme offers the benefit of lowering the emittance with weaker quadrupoles, it tends to further lower the momentum compaction factor [S]

In the past, studies of beam dynamics in the low alpha regime were intentionally pursued in the light source storage ring community [M, and references therein] in the attempt to produce short bunches that were requested by specific users, or to produce coherent synchrotron radiation (CSR) generated by the former. The operation at low alpha however suffers from significant coherent instability, reducing significantly the stored current [C]. As a consequence, the low α lattices are potentially prone to collective instabilities. For this reason, there is a trend today to prefer tuning the ring to negative α with a much larger magnitude to avoid the issues of isochronicity (small α). This strategy is proposed in the design of SLS-II and in turn brings about the benefit of lowering the sextupole strengths to correct the chromaticity. However, the collective beam dynamics of large negative α regime in a ultra-low emittance ring is a domain that must yet be well explored both theoretically and experimentally.

1.3 THE EXPERIMENT AT KARA

To investigate beam quality and possibility of negative momentum compaction factor operation, theoretical studies and experimental tests were performed at the KARA storage ring at KIT Karlsruhe. The ring has 4-fold symmetry where each superperiod comprises two double-bend achromat cells. In KARA, experiments to manipulate the longitudinal phase space of a stored beam have been vigorously performed, mainly to generate coherent synchrotron radiation (CSR) from longitudinally compressed electron bunches [J]. As an extension of such beam manipulation, we have designed a negative α lattice for the KARA ring. To have negative α it is necessary to modify drastically the dispersion function from the usual setup. The idea is to stretch it to have larger amplitude with positive and negative values. It was possible to find realistic lattice functions for the negative α operation with the estimated α value of -2.22×10^{-3} .

With positive α , it is possible to gradually transform a normal α lattice to low alpha unless a strong resonance is crossed during the transition. With negative α , however, it is quite difficult to perform such a gradual change as we must cross over the so-called transition instability that occurs when α equals zero. Therefore, we had to perform beam injection in negative α from the beginning instead starting with a well tuned lattice at positive α . From the designed lattice functions of negative α , we tried to find a set of conditions for injection kickers. In the KARA ring, we have three horizontal kickers for beam injection. After the calculation based on a response matrix method and a beam tracking simulation, we could find sets of realistic parameters for the injection kickers. Considering the horizontal beam position and angle at the exit of an injection septum in the KARA ring, we concluded that beam injection under negative α is possible.

Injection in the negative α was made at 500 MeV, the normal value for daily operation at KARA. To modify the Twiss functions we varied five families of quadrupoles. The theory indicates that operation in negative α may lead to head-tail instability if the chromaticity is positive due to the negative head-tail phase with positive chromaticity. With negative α , it is therefore necessary to vary sextupoles to make the chromaticity negative. At the beginning of the ring commissioning, we switched off all of the sextupoles to make the situation simpler. As mentioned above, the dispersion function in the negative α lattice has larger amplitudes all around the ring; typically, the positive/negative peak values are 1.7/-1.3 m, which made beam injection in negative α rather difficult. In addition to this, there are sextupoles inside the injection bump orbit section in the KARA ring, that complicate further the closure of the orbit bump during injection. Because of both effects, it was not easy and simple to get the first stored beam in the KARA ring in negative α an stored beam was achieved only after further adjustment of the horizontal correctors. The stored current was less than 10 μ A when all the sextupoles were off, and about 30 μ A when they were properly optimised. A streak camera image of the bunch train stored in these conditions is reported in Fig. 3.1

These tests are a necessary prerequisite for further investigation and optimisation of the stored current necessary to investigate the limit posed in the operation of negative alpha lattices. A logical next step would be an attempt to improve the injection rate in the negative α optics. The most probable reason for the poor injection efficiency could be a mismatch of kick angles for the three injection kicker magnets. The other reason could be a mismatch between electron beam parameters from the injector and those of the KARA ring. In the negative α , a subtle energy mismatch could cause severe beam losses because of a larger dispersion amplitude, though such a small mismatch may not be able to cause problems in normal α beam injection. Scanning central beam energy of the KARA ring very slightly could be one of the promising ideas.

Fig. 3.1: Streak camera image of the beam stored in negative alpha at KARA. Time scales are horizontal 100 ms, vertical 600 ps.

After getting a higher beam current, we will move to experiments that mainly aim at collective effects in the negative α beam. One of the important subjects to study would be the head-tail instability. To relax the instability in the negative α operation we need less sextupole field strength because of negative natural chromaticity. This operating condition could lead to significant expansion of dynamic aperture because of the less nonlinear field by sextupoles. A potential well distortion due to broad-band impedance would be another interesting issue to examine.

4. Future plans / Conclusion / relation to other ARIES work

First beam tests towards the commissioning and operation of ultra-low emittance rings have been initiated. The activity of the WP7 Task 4.1 will continue by promoting further tests to answer the questions left open and to provide a review of the strategy tools and diagnostics necessary for the successful commissioning on the next generation of ultra low emittance rings. A key issue to be tested is related to the procedure for first turn threading, beam based alignment, LOCO-type of algorithms and turn-by-turn data, in such ultra-low emittance ring. In fact the tight demands on alignment of such rings have been relaxed on the assumption that careful commissioning strategies [Sa] can be devised and extensively tested before commissioning starts. Numerical simulations show that such tools will remain powerful and relevant to the optimisation of ultra low emittance rings with their specific challenges, however a full experimental proof is still lacking.

FIRST BEAM TESTS FOR LOW EMITTANCE RINGS

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The commissioning workshop under preparation at KIT in February 2019 will review past experience, review of the main procedures and establish the suitability to the case of ultra-low emittance rings. WP7 Task 7.4 will address these issues by providing support via networking, topical workshop and staff exchanges. It is expected that these activities will support the commissioning of the upcoming rings ESRF-EBS [**R**] and Sirius [**Ro**] planned for 2020.

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Annex: Glossary

Acronym	Definition
CDR	Conceptual Design Report
CRS	Coherent Synchrotron Radiation
CT	Current Transformers
DA	Dynamic Aperture
DBA	Double-Bend-Achromats
EPICS	Experimental Physics and Industrial Control System
IBS	Intra-Beam-Scattering
KARA	Karlsruhe Research Accelerator
KIT	Karlsruhe Institut für Technologie
LER	Low Emittance Ring
LOCO	Linear Optics from Closed Orbits
MBA	Multi-Bend-Achromats
RF	Radio Frequency
RULE	Rings for Ultra Low Emittance
SLS-II	Swiss Light Source 2 (upgrade project)
TBA	Triple-Bend-Achromats